

A novel one flask synthesis of 1,2-substituted 5-imidazolones

Purbasha Dasgupta and Archana Taunk*

Department of Chemistry, R. D. National and W. A. Science College, Mumbai-400 050, India

E-mail : purbasha_3_1@yahoo.com, archanaa4@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 15 December 2008, revised 8 June 2009, accepted 7 July 2009

Abstract : One flask synthesis of 4-arylmethylene-1-phenyl-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-ones was achieved by the phenyl isothiocyanate-mediated condensation of *N*-acetyl glycine with aromatic aldehydes.

Keywords : 5-Imidazolones, synthesis, aromatic aldehydes.

Introduction

In organic synthesis, imidazoline units are used as intermediates¹, chiral auxiliaries², chiral catalysis³ and ligands for asymmetric catalysis⁴. A number of methods have been reported for the synthesis of imidazolines. As a part of our investigation for developing efficient method for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds, we report here a synthetic method for the preparation of 5-imidazolones from aromatic aldehydes and anilines.

Results and discussion

The condensation of *N*-acetyl glycine (1) with phenyl isothiocyanate was found to give aceturanilide (6) with a view to confirming the intermediacy of 5. *N*-Acetyl glycine was cyclocondensed with phenyl isothiocyanate in the presence of aromatic aldehyde (3), using pyridine as a catalyst and the product was found to be 4-arylmethylene-1-phenyl-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-one (4), the yield of which depended on the molar ratio of the aldehyde (3) taken. Formation of 2-oxazolin-5-one (5) has been confirmed by isolating oxazolone based products in the reaction (Scheme 1). Aniline, liberated during the process, would bring about aminolysis of 5, affording thereby anilide (6). In the presence of an aldehyde, aniline would be trapped as an imine (7) which would then condense with 5, forming 4-arylmethylene-2-methyl-2-oxazolin-5-one (8) and subsequently gives 4-arylmethylene-2-styryl-2-oxazolin-5-one (9) which proves that the C-2 methyl group is reactive enough to undergo condensation with aromatic aldehyde or its imine. Whereas 10 would give the 2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-one directly (4), but the cyclisation of 1 would give 2-methyl-2-oxazolin-5-one (5) by using ethyl chloroformate in the presence of triethylamine in dry benzene which would subsequently con-

Scheme 3

Note

dense with aromatic aldehydes or Schiff bases, leading to the formation of 1-substituted-4-arylmethylene-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-ones (12).

Some of the 4-arylmethylene-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-ones reported here are known in the literature, but their synthesis are usually carried out in a step-wise fashion^{5,6}, hence requiring longer time. The present one-flask synthesis is simple and quick and the work-up is easy.

The products were analyzed by spectral data and elemental analysis. The absorption band near ν 1710 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum accounts for the carbonyl group of the imidazolone ring, and the coupling constant of 14 Hz for two vicinal olefinic protons near the aromatic region in the PMR spectrum supports the *trans*-geometry of the styryl moiety.

The relevant data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. 1-Substituted 4-arylmethylene-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-one

Compd.	Ar	R	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	IR (cm^{-1})	Elemental analysis	NMR
1	Ph	Ph	36.13	240	1717, 3943, 3691, 2927	C, 78.26; H, 5.43; N, 7.60	7.35–7.55 (13H, m, Ar-H), 7.7 (3H, d, Ph-CH=CH), 8.65 (1H, s, Ph-OH), 8.88 (1H, s, Ph-OH)
2	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	53	225	3345, 1600, 2924	C, 69.19; H, 5.09; N, 6.20	-
3	2-OH, C ₆ H ₄	Ph	68.19	201	1681, 3272, 2923	C, 76.15; H, 5.21; N, 7.09	-
4	4-OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	Ph	47.57	112	3645, 2922, 1703, 1639	C, 75.65; H, 5.31; N, 7.10	-

Table 2. 1-Substituted 4-arylmethylene-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-one (using acetyl glycine by alternate method)

Compd.	Ar	R	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	IR (cm^{-1})	Elemental analysis	NMR
1	Ph	Ph	63.34	224	1717, 3943, 3691, 2927	C, 78.26; H, 5.43; N, 7.60	-
2	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	41.38	220	1718, 3143, 2925	C, 74.90; H, 4.42; N, 7.27	-
3	Ph	4-HOCC ₆ H ₄	50.12	149	1729, 3351, 2925	C, 76.32; H, 5.13; N, 7.23	-
4	2-OH, C ₆ H ₄	Ph	44.49	210	1681, 3272, 2923	C, 75.00; H, 5.20; N, 7.28	-
5	Ph	N-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅	53.16	Above 280	3391, 2923, 1558	C, 76.12; H, 5.09; N, 7.12	-

Table-2 (contd.)

6	2-OH, C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	65	103	1897, 1583, 1608, 2924	C, 74.67; H, 4.93; N, 7.19	6.94–7.1 (8H, m, Ph-OH), 7.4–7.5 (4H, m, Ph-Cl), 6.66 (1H, d, Ph- CH=CH), 8.9 (1H, s, Ph-OH)
7	2-OH, C ₆ H ₄	4-HOOC C ₆ H ₄	70.67	252	3346, 1677, 2924	C, 75.13; H, 5.03; N, 7.31	6.8 (1H, d, Ph- CH=CH), 8.1 (1H, d, Ph-CH=CH), 6.9–7.1 (4H, m, Ph-COOH), 7.4–7.75 (8H, m, Ph-OH)
8	2-OH, C ₆ H ₄	N-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅	38	Above 280	3346, 1677, 2924	C, 74.67; H, 5.26; N, 6.98	–
9	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	Ph	42.05	220	3345, 1600, 2924	C, 72.46; H, 5.31; N, 6.77	–
10	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	30.29	244	3338, 1651, 2922	C, 73.51; H, 4.96; N, 6.35	–
11	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	4-HOOC C ₆ H ₄	62.78	Above 280	3315, 1678, 2926	C, 73.19; H, 5.42; N, 6.51	–
12	Ph	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	47.33	262	3290, 1654, 2924	C, 77.23; H, 5.39; N, 7.19	–
13	2-OH, C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55.23	78	3446, 1621, 2922	C, 74.54; H, 5.67; N, 6.61	–
14	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	69.01	233	3400, 1621, 2925	C, 75.18; H, 5.51; N, 6.91	–
15	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	54	195	3369, 2854, 1549, 2925	C, 75.65; H, 5.31; N, 7.10	–
16	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-HOOC C ₆ H ₄	46.93	245	1594, 3390, 2854, 2924	C, 74.63; H, 5.19; N, 6.87	–
17	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	79.18	130	–	C, 75.18; H, 5.23; N, 7.12	–

Experimental

All chemicals used were of LR grade and the melting points reported were taken in an open capillary tube and are uncorrected. All yields refer to isolated product after purification. The products were confirmed by IR spectra. The ¹H NMR spectra of the samples were also recorded.

Formation of 4-arylmethylene-1-phenyl-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-ones (4) :

General procedure : Method A :

Phenyl isothiocyanate (1.2 mol), *N*-acetyl glycine (1.0 mol), aromatic aldehyde (2.0 mol) and pyridine (0.1 ml/

g of *N*-acetyl glycine) were heated together at 160–170 °C for 30 min. The mixture was washed with light petroleum (b.p. 40–60 °C), sodium bicarbonate solution and water. The crude product was recrystallized from ethanol or glacial acetic acid. The reaction has been outlined in Schemes 1 and 2. Relevant data are given in Table 1.

An alternate method was also tried to prepare 4, for which the condensation of 4-arylmethylene-2-methyl-2-oxazolin-5-ones (8) was carried out with different anilines and substituted aldehydes to give 4.

Note

Synthesis of 1-substituted-4-arylmethylene-2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-ones (12) (alternate method) :

Method B :

To a suspension of *N*-acetyl glycine acid (1.0 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml/g of *N*-acetyl glycine), triethylamine (2.2 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (1.1 mol) was added and the mixture was shaken at room temperature until the crystals of acid dissolved and triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and washed with dry benzene. The filtrate and washings were combined and aniline (1.1 mol), glacial acetic acid (~ 5 ml) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 10–15 min. After cooling aromatic aldehydes (1.1 mol), was added with glacial acetic acid (~ 10 ml) and a small amount of freshly fused sodium acetate was added as a catalyst. It was refluxed for 2.5 h. After evaporating the solvent it was recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. The reaction has been outlined in Scheme 3. The relevant data are given in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Mr. M. R. Mulwani, Head, Department of Chemistry, and the authorities of R. D.

National and W. A. Science College for providing us with the necessary facilities. Our thanks to the IIT, Department of Chemistry, Mumbai for providing us with the NMR and IR spectra.

References

1. F. Rondu, G. Le Bihan, X. Wang, A. Lamouri, E. Touboul, G. Dive, T. Bellahsene, B. Pfeiffer, P. Renard, B. Guardiola-Lemaitre, D. Manechez, L. Penicaud, A. Ktorza and J. J. Godfroid, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1997, **40**, 3793.
2. M. Ueno, K. Imaizumi, T. Sugita, I. Takata and M. Takeshita, *Int. J. Immunopharmac.*, 1995, **17**, 597.
3. (a) T. Hayashi, E. Kishi, V. A. Soloshonok and Y. Uozumi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 4969; (b) M. E. Jung and A. Huang, *Org. Lett.*, 2000, **2**, 2659.
4. (a) E. J. Corey and M. J. Grogan, *Org. Lett.*, 1999, **1**, 157; (b) T. Isobe, K. Fukuda, Y. Araki and T. Ishikawa, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, 243.
5. M. S. Reddy, P. Hanumanthu and C. V. Ratnam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 646.
6. A. K. Mukerjee and P. Kumar, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1982, **60**, 317.